

Hazard Control Practices among Clinical Staff of Dental Clinics in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study discussed hazards control practices among clinical staff of dental clinics in Rivers State. Four research questions and four hypotheses were formulated. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study with a population of 209 drawn through multi-stage sampling procedures which included simple random sampling and purposive sampling procedures. The respondents consisted of dentists, dental surgery technicians/dental nurses, therapists and technologists of dental clinics in Rivers State. Instrument for data collection was a researcher's developed questionnaire titled "Health Hazards and Control Practices Questionnaire (HACOPQ)" with 18-item closed-ended questions which was validated by three experts and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to obtain reliability co-efficient of 0.82. Data were presented in tables of frequency and analyzed using percentage, mean, standard deviation for research questions while ANOVA and Z-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.50 alpha level using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The study identified hazards control practices among clinical staff in the dental clinics. The tested hypotheses revealed statistical significant difference with control practices among dental clinical staff in the dental clinics. It was concluded that hazards in dental clinics in Rivers State can be controlled. Therefore, the study recommended among others that managers of the dental clinics in Rivers State should provide CCTV cameras to monitor clinical staff compliance to the various hazards control practices in the dental clinics.

Keywords: control, clinical staff, dental clinic, hazard, practice